

A New Operational Matrix of Fibonacci Polynomials for Solving a Class of Distributed Order Fractional Differential Equations

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ABSTRACT. Here, we propose a numerical method for solving linear distributed-order fractional differential equations. Distributed order fractional derivative operational matrix and fractional derivative operational matrix for Fibonacci polynomials are presented. Using the operational matrices and Galerkin method, the problem is converted into a system of algebraic equations. Several examples are tests to investigate the efficiency of the technique.

Keywords: Distributed-order fractional derivative operational matrix, Distributed order fractional equation, Fibonacci polynomial, Galerkin method.

AMS Mathematical Subject Classification [2010]: 65D15, 11B39, 68M14.

1. Introduction

Firstly, distributed-order of fractional derivative is presented by Caputo [3]. Next, this concept is developed by himself and some mathematicians. This concept is used in mathematical modeling of some phenomena, then this has been considered by several researchers. Torvik and Bagley [1] investigated on the existence of the solution of distributed-order equations. The authors in [5] perused stability analysis of distributed-order of fractional differential equations. However, there is a difficult task to analytically treat these problems. Thus, it is required that a numerical scheme is established. Therefore, some numerical method for solving this class of equations have been proposed. A method based on Legendre polynomials [6] and a modified method proposed in [9] are samples of computational methods presented by some researchers.

2. Preliminaries

DEFINITION 2.1. The Riemann-Liouville fractional integration operator of order $\gamma \geq 0$ of $f \in C_\eta, \eta > -1$ is defined as [7]

$$(1) \quad I^\gamma u(t) = \begin{cases} \frac{1}{\Gamma(\gamma)} \int_0^t u(s)(t-s)^{\gamma-1} ds, & \gamma > 0, t > 0, \\ u(t), & \gamma = 0. \end{cases}$$

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DEFINITION 2.2. The Caputo fractional derivative of order γ of $f \in C_\eta, \eta > -1$ is defined as [7]

$$(2) \quad D^\gamma u(t) = \begin{cases} \frac{1}{\Gamma(n-\gamma)} \int_0^t u^{(n)}(s)(t-s)^{n-\gamma-1} ds, & n-1 < \gamma \leq n, n \in N, \\ u(t), & \gamma = 0. \end{cases}$$

Also, we have

- 1) $D^\gamma c = 0$, where c is constant.
- 2) $I^\gamma D^\gamma u(t) = u(t) - \sum_{i=0}^{n-1} u^{(i)}(0) \frac{t^i}{i!}$.
- 3) $D^\gamma t^k = \begin{cases} \frac{\Gamma(k+1)}{\Gamma(k+1-\gamma)} t^{k-\gamma}, & k \geq \gamma, \\ 0, & k < \gamma. \end{cases}$

2.1. Fibonacci Polynomials and Their Properties. Fibonacci polynomials defined as the following form [8]

$$(3) \quad F_m(x) = \sum_{i=0}^{\lfloor m/2 \rfloor} \binom{m-i}{i} x^{m-2i}, \quad m \geq 0.$$

Here, the first m -terms of the Fibonacci polynomials are used to proposed an approximation. Then, an arbitrary function $u(t) \in L^2[0, 1]$ may be approximate as follows

$$(4) \quad u(t) \simeq \sum_{j=0}^M u_j F_j(t) = U^T \Psi(t),$$

subject to

$$(5) \quad U = [u_0, u_1, \dots, u_M]^T, \quad \Psi(t) = [F_0(t), F_1(t), \dots, F_M(t)]^T.$$

The coefficient vector $U = (u_j)$ is given by $U^T = \Delta^T D^{-1}$, where $D = \langle \Psi, \Psi \rangle$, $\Delta = \langle u, \Psi \rangle$.

2.2. Caputo Derivative Operational Matrix of Fibonacci Polynomials. This subsection is devoted to construct the Caputo derivative operational matrix for Fibonacci polynomials. The Caputo derivative of the vector $\Psi(t)$ can be expressed by

$$(6) \quad D^\gamma \Psi(t) \simeq D^{(\gamma)} \Psi(t).$$

$D^{(\gamma)}$ is the $(M+1) \times (M+1)$ operational matrix of Caputo fractional derivative.

Now, we obtain this operational matrix. Using Eq. (3) and considering the properties of Caputo derivative, we have

$$(7) \quad \begin{aligned} D^\gamma F_m(t) &= \sum_{i=0}^{\lfloor m/2 \rfloor} \binom{m-i}{i} D^\gamma t^{m-2i} \\ &= \sum_{i=0}^{\lfloor m/2 \rfloor} \binom{m-i}{i} \eta_{m-2i-\gamma}(t), \end{aligned}$$

where

$$\eta_{m-2i-\gamma}(t) = \begin{cases} \frac{\Gamma(m-2i+1)}{\Gamma(m-2i+1-\gamma)} t^{m-2i-\gamma}, & m-2i \geq \gamma, \\ 0, & m-2i < \gamma. \end{cases}$$

and $m \geq 0$.

Now, by expanding the above equation regarding Fibonacci polynomials, we have

$$(8) \quad D^\gamma F_m(t) \simeq \phi_{m,\gamma}^T \Psi(t).$$

Then, we achieve the following relation:

$$D^{(\gamma)} = [\phi_{m,\gamma}^T], \quad m = 0, 1, \dots, M.$$

2.3. Distributed-Order Fractional Derivative Operational Matrix of Fibonacci Polynomials. Here, the methodology of obtaining the distributed-order fractional derivative operational matrix is presented. This operational matrix is presented as follows:

$$(9) \quad D^{\tau(\gamma)} \Psi(t) \simeq \Theta_{\tau(\gamma)} \Psi(t),$$

where $D^{\tau(\gamma)} u(t) = \int_a^b \tau(\gamma) D^\gamma u(t) d\gamma$. Considering definition of $D^{\tau(\gamma)} u(t)$ and Eq. (8) and utilizing the Gauss-Legendre numerical integration for evaluating the existing integration, we derive

$$(10) \quad \begin{aligned} D^{\tau(\gamma)} F_m(t) &= \int_a^b \tau(\gamma) D^\gamma F_m(t) d\gamma \simeq \int_a^b \tau(\gamma) \phi_{m,\gamma}^T \Psi(t) d\gamma \\ &= \left(\int_a^b \tau(\gamma) \phi_{m,\gamma}^T d\gamma \right) \Psi(t) \\ &\simeq \frac{b-a}{2} \left(\sum_{j=1}^N \omega_j \tau\left(\frac{b-a}{2} \vartheta_j + \frac{a+b}{2}\right) \phi_{m,(\frac{b-a}{2} \vartheta_j + \frac{a+b}{2})}^T \right) \Psi(t) \\ &= \chi_{m,\tau(\gamma)}^T \Psi(t). \end{aligned}$$

Hence, we have

$$\Theta_{\tau(\gamma)} = [\chi_{m,\tau(\gamma)}^T], \quad m = 0, 1, \dots, M.$$

3. Description of the Method

Here, we consider the following distributed-order fractional differential equation (DFDE):

$$(11) \quad \int_a^b \tau(\gamma) D^\gamma u(t) d\gamma = G(t), \quad t \in [0, 1],$$

subject to the following constraints

$$(12) \quad u^{(l)}(0) = u_{0,l}, \quad l = 0, 1, \dots, [b] - 1,$$

and D^γ denotes the fractional derivative in the Caputo type of order γ . a and b are positive numbers. We approximate the function $u(t)$ by Fibonacci polynomials as follows $u(t) \simeq U^T \Psi(t)$, where U is an unknown vector and Ψ is defined in Eq. (5). Then, concerning distributed-order fractional derivative operational matrix, the considered problem can be written as

$$(13) \quad Y(t) = U^T \Theta_{\tau(\gamma)} \Psi(t) - G(t),$$

Now, we use the Galerkin method which is convergent [2]

$$(14) \quad \langle Y, F_m \rangle = 0, \quad m = 0, 1, M - l,$$

TABLE 1. Comparison of the L_2 errors in Example 4.1.

Methods	L_2 errors
Ref. [6]	
$m = 6$	2.73×10^{-5}
$m = 10$	1.84×10^{-6}
Present method	
$M = 3$	2.22507×10^{-7}

and for the initial conditions, we get

$$(15) \quad U^T D^\gamma \Psi(0) - u_{0,l} = 0, \quad l = 0, 1, \dots, [b] - 1.$$

Considering the above relations, the problem translates to a system of algebraic equations. The system is solved by applying the “Find Root” package in Mathematica software to obtain the unknown coefficients vector.

4. Illustrative Examples

EXAMPLE 4.1. Consider the following DFDE [6]

$$\int_0^1 \frac{\Gamma(\frac{7}{2} - \gamma)}{\Gamma(\frac{7}{2})} D^\gamma u(t) d\gamma = \frac{t^{\frac{3}{2}}(t-1)}{\ln(t)},$$

subject to $u(0) = 0$. The exact solution of this problem is $u(t) = t^{\frac{5}{2}}$. Table 1 reports the maximum absolute errors of the proposed technique for $M = 5$ and the results using method based on Legendre polynomials [6].

EXAMPLE 4.2. Consider the following DFDE as

$$\int_0^2 \frac{\Gamma(6 - \gamma)}{120} D^\gamma u(t) d\gamma = \frac{t^5 - t^3}{\ln(t)},$$

subject to $u(0) = u'(0) = 0$, and the exact solution of this problem is $u(t) = t^5$. L_∞ error achieved using the method for $M = 5$ is 3.75597×10^{-8} and this error for [9] for $N = 5$ is 1.06×10^{-7} .

EXAMPLE 4.3. Consider the following DFDE

$$\int_{0.2}^{1.5} \Gamma(3 - \gamma) D^\gamma u(t) d\gamma = 2\left(\frac{t^{1.8} - t^{0.5}}{\ln(t)}\right),$$

with the initial conditions $u(0) = u'(0) = 0$. The exact solution is $u(t) = t^2$. by applying the described method, we solve this problem, numerically. The absolute errors of the present method $M = 2$ is displayed in Figure 1. Also, Table 2 lists the relative errors in $u(0.9)$ ($|u_{ex}(t) - u_{ap}(t)|/|u_{ex}(t)|$) obtained by implemen the present method and method in [4].

FIGURE 1. The comparison of absolute error of the present method for $M = 2$ in Example 4.3.

TABLE 2. Comparison of the relative errors in $u(0.9)$ for Example 4.3.

Methods	Relative errors
Ref. [4]	
$k = 32, h = 0.0001$	7.34×10^{-5}
$k = 64, h = 0.0001$	1.26×10^{-5}
Present method	
$M = 4$	2.96394×10^{-11}

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